

EBFMC25-OP-87 · Evaluation of Hepatitis B Vaccination Status and Post-Vaccination Anti-HBs Response in HIV Patients

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: HBV is a major global cause of chronic liver disease and hepatocellular carcinoma. In people living with HIV, the risk of progression to severe liver outcomes is higher, making HBV vaccination essential (Zerdali, 2023). This study aims to evaluate the HBV immunization and vaccination status of individuals living with HIV.

Materials and Methods: This retrospective and observational study included individuals who visited the Adult Vaccination Polyclinic at Şişli Hamidiye Etfal Training and Research Hospital's Family Medicine Clinic within the last year and were eligible to complete all vaccine doses. The HBV serology results of HIV-positive individuals, vaccination rates among those with negative serology, adherence to the vaccination schedule, and vaccine responses were retrospectively reviewed. SPSS 25.0 was used for data analysis, and statistical significance was accepted at $p < 0.05$.

Results: A total of 184 individuals were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 39.8. The majority were male ($n=164, 89.1\%$). The mean time since diagnosis was 3.97 years. At the time of diagnosis, 67 individuals (36.4%) had positive Anti-HBs results, while 117 individuals (63.6%) had negative results. Among those with negative Anti-HBs results who required vaccination, one person had never received the vaccine. Distribution of the number of Hepatitis B vaccine doses administered to participants were given in Figure 1. Among those who received three vaccine doses, 32.8% ($n=21$) had no Anti-HBs test performed post-vaccination.

Figure 1

Among those who received three vaccine doses, 32.8% (n=21) had no Anti-HBs test performed post-vaccination. Among those who had the Anti-HBs test, 34 individuals (53.1%) had a positive result, while 9 individuals (14.1%) had a negative result. Among the individuals with negative results, 6 started the vaccination series again, and only one of them completed all three doses. After the second vaccination series, this individual's Anti-HBs level was positive. There was no significant difference between the completion of all three doses of the Hepatitis B vaccine and factors such as age, gender, or the year of diagnosis ($p>0.05$). Additionally, there was no significant difference between the Anti-HBs positivity in individuals who received all three doses of the vaccine and factors such as age, diagnosis year and gender ($p>0.05$).

Conclusion: This study shows that although the majority of HIV-infected individuals with negative HBV serology started vaccination, their adherence to the vaccination schedule remained low. Furthermore, it was found that approximately half of those who completed all three doses of the vaccine had an adequate Anti-HBs response. For individuals who did not develop an adequate response, additional doses contributed to achieving a positive response.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Vaccine response, vaccination, hepatitis B vaccine

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

The authors declared no conflicts of interest.

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Zerdali, E. (2023). Evaluation of hepatitis B vaccination status and factors affecting response to vaccination in HIV/AIDS patients. *Klimik Dergisi*, 36, 190–195. <https://www.klimikdergisi.org/en/2023/09/30/hepatitis-b-vaccine-response-in-hiv-aids-patients/>

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